

emerged *N. bakeri* and *N. lugens* brachyp-
 eters were examined. The following varia-
 tions in karyotypic features were de-
 tected:

1. Although females yield only one type of ova and males produce two types of sperm in both species, variations exist in the diploid chromosomal complement and the sex-determining mechanism (see table and figure).
2. In both species, chromosomes in gonial meiosis do not have distinct centromeres because they have diffused kinetochores. The constrictions vital for chromosomal movements and segregations during the meiotic stages are located along the length of the chromosomes. However, *N. bakeri* has relatively longer chromosomes: the shortest and the longest *N. bakeri* chromosomes are nearly 4 times longer than those of *N. lugens*. The nucleolar organizer of *N. bakeri* is its longest (143.50 mm) chromosome. In *N. lugens* it is 20.75 mm long.

These cytogenetic deviations impose pre- and post-mating barriers to effective hybridization between *N. bakeri* and *N. lugens*, and are additional taxonomic indices for differentiating the two species. □

Autosomes and sex chromosomes of planthopper species from *Leersia hexandra* (L.) Swartz. Sex chromosomes are indicated by arrows.

Incidence of brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål on IR50 at graded levels of fertilization at Aduthurai

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IR50 was recently introduced in Tamil Nadu. We studied the response of this variety under graded levels of fertilization and BPH damage in a randomized block design with eight treatments and three replications. BPH population was recorded 80 d after transplanting (see table).

BPH population increased with fertilizer levels. Maximum BPH/hill was 106 when 150 kg N/ha was applied. The BPH population was lowest (5/hill) when no fertilizer was applied. P and K did not significantly influence BPH population.

Incidence of BPH under graded levels of fertilization, Aduthurai, India.

Fertilization ^a			BPH (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)
N	P	K		
0	0	0	5	4.1
50	0	0	50	4.7
100	0	0	53	5.5
150	0	0	106	4.6
50	11	21	28	4.7
100	22	42	54	5.4
150	33	62	84	5.0
0	22	42	5	5.0
CD			47.8	1.0

^aFertilization: 50% N = basal application, 25% N = topdressing at tillering, 25% N = topdressing at panicle initiation; P and K = basal applications.

At 100 kg N/ha with or without P and K, yield was 5.5 t/ha although the BPH population was above the economic threshold level. □

Effect of carbofuran and nitrogen on leafhopper incidence

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The effects of combined application of carbofuran and nitrogen on leafhopper *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (G.) incidence was studied at Tamil Nadu RRI Sep 1982-Jan 83. The field trial was in a split-plot design with three replications. Thirty-day-old IR20 seedlings were planted in 20-m² plots at 20 × 10-cm spacing. Carbofuran was incorporated at 0.5 and 0.75 kg ai/ha with a basal application of nitrogen as urea at planting. Carbofuran was topdressed at 0.5, 0.75, and 1.0 kg ai/ha with the first topdressing of urea 15 days after transplanting (15 DT). N levels 0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 kg/ha were applied